

System Level Reliability Analyses and Predictions in a Varying Stress Environment

Dona Johnson, NAVAIR, Department of the Navy

David W. Coit, Ph. D., Department of Industrial & Systems Engineering, Rutgers University

Robert Kosaka, Department of Industrial & Systems Engineering, Rutgers University

Keith Megow, NAVAIR, Department of the Navy

Key Words: Stress-sensitive reliability prediction, Mission profiles, Aircraft launch and recovery equipment

ABSTRACT

New flexible methods have been developed to predict reliability and estimate failure time distribution parameters for equipment and systems that are to be exposed to more stressful and diverse usage conditions in the future. Decades ago, the design reference mission for steam catapults and arresting gear on aircraft carriers was quite simple. The design engineers of these systems had a good understanding of the loads and added factors of safety to be cautious. Move ahead to the present, the mixture of aircraft has changed drastically, sortie rate has increased and so has the kinetic energy imparted to these critical systems. This has led to a need to develop a more generalized and flexible reliability predictive tool. This tool can be described as a stress-sensitive Weibull distribution. The entire process is outlined for this innovative technique. It includes the options for several methods of analysis. The base model is a Weibull distribution based solely on failure data without modifications. The first method is also a Weibull distribution, but the Weibull scale parameter is modified by a stress ratio, using end speed and the aircraft weight. The second method uses mean and standard deviation of end speed and aircraft weight to modify the Weibull scale parameter. These scale parameter modifiers are calculated based on an assumed general log-linear model and maximum likelihood estimation tools. The third method decouples any correlation that may exist between aircraft weight and end speed by binning aircraft launches into groups and calculating their proportion of the total. Once evaluated, these methods are able to extrapolate future failures at different levels of stress all across these critical systems.

1 INTRODUCTION

In this paper, we present a new modeling approach that can be used for components and systems being subjected to higher loads and stresses due to changing missions and shifting proportions of aircraft users. Air wing changes (higher launch energy) and Aircraft Launch and Recovery Equipment (ALRE) aging affect aircraft carrier operational availability. This research explores several stress sensitive reliability

models (SSRM) that estimate future system reliability based on currently available maintenance/repair data and anticipated future changes in ALRE. Since the ALRE is flight critical, the majority of data is preventative in nature. The goal is to aid resource allocation decisions for both equipment sparing and engineering design efforts to address ALRE availability.

1.1 Literature Review

A survey of research pertaining to the topic of failure time distributions, changing with variable stress, was conducted. Research revealed that simple failure times or cycles-to-failure might be inadequate to describe the system under study. Research conducted by Hada et al (Ref. 1) studied the usage of covariates for changing stress profiles. This work shed insight into the usage of reliability models for future reliability predictions.

Research by Wang et al (Ref. 2) used a failure model that implemented load applications as a model parameter. In their research they applied randomized loads and classified them accordingly. Similar work done by Zhang et al (Ref. 3) modeled reliability of electrical systems due to electrical, mechanical, temperature stresses. Their models considered a multitude of stresses as well as simply the aging of the electrical system. Wang et al (Ref. 4) focuses on using the frequency of loading to create failure distribution parameters. This approach considered the use of load-strength interference and theory of order statistics when developing models. Prasad (Ref. 6) conducted research regarding the usage of system and environmental stresses when creating reliability models. Prasad (Ref. 6) referred to these stresses as covariates when applied to the model. Attadari et al (Ref. 7) also utilized covariates when analyzing automotive component reliability. Their work used a vector of covariates that indexed specific operating conditions.

Research conducted by Zhang et al (Ref. 5) used reliability and life models to create and optimize maintenance strategies. These strategies were created to both optimize system downtime as well as minimize costs. Work done by Zhang et al Ref. (8) focused on maximum likelihood estimation to determine Weibull parameters. They developed

an iterative flow chart to describe the process of maximization.

2 MISSION STATEMENT

For ALRE systems, the percentage of heavy aircraft has increased and will continue to do so in the future. In addition, there is also a greater variance of loading due to the variety of aircraft and configurations. Multiple variants of the F-18, F-35 introduction as well as a cadre of existing aircraft all lead to increased and varied stresses on the ALRE. Although this affords flexibility and efficiency to the U.S Navy, it results in greater and more varied launch energy and stress. The SSRM has to address both increased stress as well as higher stress variability effects on the ALRE equipment.

As noted, current ALRE repair/failure and launch data is critical in allowing accurate ALRE reliability analysis. However repair and launch data is must go through a quality control process before it is useable for reliability predictions. This has been addressed through filtering and improved recording standardization. Section 3.0 addresses the filtering and data quality analysis in further detail. Since ALRE system maintenance effects launch tempo and is difficult to access physically, many of the repair actions are done on a periodic basis or for convenience when other maintenance is performed. This adds non-failure or suspension data rather than failure data for the part/system in question. Therefore, the model also has to accommodate failure, repair and suspension data. This varied data is accommodated with the Reliasoft ALTA software.

3 MISSION CHARACTERISTICS

3.1 Data Collection

The fleet keeps aircraft shot and recovery logs (ASRL) for every aircraft carrier. This provides a reasonably accurate count of the number of launch and recovery cycles along with performance data including vehicle weight and speed. Not every data field in ASRL was useful for this study; the following was used for analyzing launcher equipment: catapult number, shot number, date, aircraft type, aircraft weight and end speed. Several strategies are employed to ensure good data quality. To consider values outside the acceptable ranges for weight or end speed for a particular aircraft, data is filtered and replaced when necessary with calculated average data. Consultation with naval field service engineers and retired maintenance personnel is used to explore and resolve anomalies when they are discovered.

Figure 1 presents a frequency distribution from a catapult of interest, both of these curves span some time period. The solid black line is the first interval and the dotted line is the second interval of time. It can be observed that there is a shift of mean aircraft weight.

Aircraft weight and speed can be used to estimate stress loads on ALRE systems. This data can be applied in various methods, explained in later sections, to estimate the change in reliability of several key ALRE subsystems as a function of estimated stress loads. Baseline reliability for these

subsystems was calculated using Weibull analysis of fleet maintenance and repair logs. The logs are mined to identify three categories of maintenance actions. They are preventive, corrective, and inspections. ALRE maintenance personnel are tasked to take preventive action on a scheduled basis (calendar or shot/trap count) to maintain equipment. During these preventive actions, measurements are taken to verify that their equipment is within specification. If upon inspection anything fails, they perform corrective action. Sometimes for convenience, they change-out equipment since their systems are already opened up even though they have not failed. All of this data is recorded into their daily maintenance logs that were analyzed for this study. For the purposes of this study, a “failure” is defined as when a part is out of tolerance - not when there has been a catastrophic failure. It is rare that parts ever see end-of-life and this is intentional to maintain a high degree of safety. This analysis uses both the stresses from ASRL and the fleet maintenance log failures together. These methods go one step further; they use these two building blocks to predict the failure rates at a point in the future.

Figure 1: Frequency Distribution of Mean Weight

3.2 Data Binning

Data binning is a critical aspect in the model building process. The general idea of data binning is grouping similar system loads based on their respective stresses. By grouping multiple loads in a single bin it is implied that they all affect the system in a similar manner.

Figure 2: Binning Diagram

The main advantage of grouping loads into bins is that it makes parameter calculations easier. Binning also allows stressor independence and normalization, affording more stability to the model covariates.

Figure 2 represent a sample binning diagram. It can be seen that bins are determined by their thresholds of two different stresses. In practice it is possible to have fewer or more stresses to determine bin groupings. If a certain load is within a bin's thresholds it is considered to be part of that bin.

Mathematically each bin represents a percentage of the total number of loads seen in a given interval. This can be seen in Equation 3.1. These bin proportions (x_i) can then be used for reliability analyses.

$$x_i = \frac{\text{total number of loads in bin } i}{\text{total number of loads in interval}} \quad (3.1)$$

For our study, different bin definitions and binning approaches were studied and tested. The two most promising binning approaches were defined as Versions 1 and 5.

4 MODELING APPROACH

Three generation modeling approaches were developed, considered and compared. The most promising involved the use of mission bins.

4.1 Mean Weight and End Speed

The first and most simple model considers mean weight and end speed as the two stressors for the model. These two attributes are determined for the interval between failures or maintenance actions and must be computed by means of a database. The general equation for this model can be seen in Equation 4.1. For this model both alphas must be negative for the model to have a valid physical interpretation. A number close to zero would indicate a non-stress sensitive component which may be possible if sufficiently isolated from the stress path (e.g., electrical switches, sensors, etc.) A positive value for any alpha would indicate a positive correlation with reliability, which is known to be untrue for the system under study.

$$f(t) = \frac{\beta}{\eta} \left(\frac{t}{\eta} \right)^{\beta-1} e^{-\left(\frac{t}{\eta} \right)^\beta} \quad (4.1)$$

$$\eta = \eta_0 \exp(\alpha_1 \mu_{\text{Aircraft Weight}} + \alpha_2 \mu_{\text{End Speed}})$$

4.2 Means and Standard Deviations

A supplemental approach to the mean weight and end speed model is the addition of standard deviations. In this model there are four factors to consider: mean weight, mean end speed, weight standard deviation, and end speed standard deviation. In a similar fashion all alphas for this model must be negative to be consistent with engineering analyses. The procedure to calculate stress values is the same as the mean approach. Equation 4.2 illustrates the addition of the standard deviation to the reliability model.

$$f(t) = \frac{\beta}{\eta} \left(\frac{t}{\eta} \right)^{\beta-1} e^{-\left(\frac{t}{\eta} \right)^\beta} \quad (4.2)$$

$$\eta = \eta_0 \exp(\alpha_1 \mu_{\text{Aircraft Weight}} + \alpha_2 \sigma_{\text{Aircraft Weight}} + \alpha_3 \mu_{\text{End Speed}} + \alpha_4 \sigma_{\text{End Speed}})$$

4.3 Constrained Maximum Likelihood Maximization

The modeling approach for constrained maximum likelihood maximization is a multi-step process. For simplicity, the steps in this section have been applied to a sample version of the bins. It is important to note, however, that this approach holds true to any version of bins. It is also critical to emphasize that the order in which these steps are in is essential to the success of this approach. Figure 4 illustrates the steps that are taken in this process.

Figure 4: Flow Diagram

There are two key points to note before beginning the process. Firstly, the initial bins must be determined before the process can begin. This process does not aid in the initial creation of bins. This must be done based on engineering analyses and numerical assessment of flight launch data. Secondly, it is important to understand the relationship between Bins. By this it is meant that the relative impact from one bin to another must be known. In this example, for instance, it is known that relative bin stress increases in ascending bin order. In other cases, it might be the reverse, but it still must be taken into consideration.

4.4 Model and Constraints with Baseline

It is important to first declare the objective and constraints of the model. One important point to note is without the use of a baseline the alphas do not have to be negative. Instead they must follow the constraints shown in Equation 4.3. The general concept of these constraints is that the alphas must have descending values. This is because historical information for this example indicates that as bins ascend, the relative stress increases. These constraints are the basis on which the entire approach is based on.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Max} \quad & L(\mathbf{a}) \\ \text{st} \quad & \alpha_i \geq \alpha_{i+1} \\ & \mathbf{a} = (\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n) \end{aligned} \quad (4.3)$$

where n is number of bins

It is also worth noting that the alphas in Equation 4.3 are related to the two parameter Weibull function. This is illustrated in Equation 4.4.

$$f(t) = \frac{\beta}{\eta} \left(\frac{t}{\eta} \right)^{\beta-1} e^{-\left(\frac{t}{\eta}\right)^\beta}$$

$$\eta = \eta_0 \exp(\alpha_1 x_1 + \alpha_2 x_2 + \dots) \quad (4.4)$$

x_i = relative frequency of bin i

Step 1: Initial maximum Likelihood Estimation

Step 1 involves solving the ALTA model without the usage of constraints. By this it is meant that the model is run with every parameter, or in this case bin, being used. This provides all of the necessary information to evaluate the constraints outlined in Equation 4.1. Table 1 shows a sample output of alphas for Version 5 of the binning approach. It can be seen that each bin has a corresponding alpha. In the event that the model does not run with all the Bins a different approach using a baseline must be used. This approach is outlined in section 4.2 of this document.

Table 1: Alphas from Initial Run

Bin 1	Bin 2	Bin 3	Bin 4	Bin 5
α_1	α_2	α_3	α_4	α_5

Step 2: Compute Constraint Violations

After the completion of Step 1, the outputted alphas are used to compute the constraint violations. These violations show to what extent the alphas digress from the given rules. Equation 4.5 outlines the process for computing constraint violations. By this it is meant that the difference between each set of alphas is computed. This approach holds true for any Bin Version; however the number of violations computed would change.

$$\Delta_l = \alpha_{i+1} - \alpha_i$$

$$\text{for } l = (1, 2, 3, \dots) \quad (4.5)$$

where l = total number of bins-1

Step 3: Determine the Highest Constraint Violation

Once all of the constraint violations have been computed the next step is to find the largest value of Δ_l . This can be seen mathematically in Equation 4.6. The rationale behind this is that the largest Δ_l is causing the greatest inconsistency to the model because engineering analyses support the contention that the alphas are decreasing (which decreases reliability as stress increases). By finding the maximum Δ_l it is possible to locate the cause; α_l . The corresponding alpha parameter is then renamed to avoid confusion. This can be seen in Equation 4.7.

$$\max_j \Delta_l = \Delta_j \quad (4.6)$$

$$j = k$$

$$\alpha_j = \alpha_k \quad (4.7)$$

Step 4: Add Additional Constraint

The results of Step 3 indicate what bins must be addressed. Unlike other modeling techniques parameters cannot simply be discarded. Therefore, a different approach must be taken. This new approach is to combine the two Bins that created the largest value of Δ_l . This is mathematically shown in Equation 4.8. The reason for this stems from the constraint violations. These violations indicate that ALTA

cannot distinguish one parameter from the other. Because they cannot be differentiated the logical assumption would be to combine them.

$$\alpha_k = \alpha_{k+1} \quad (4.8)$$

These new alphas are applied to the reliability model in Equation 4.9. It can be seen that Bins k and $k+1$ now share a common alpha value. This combination approach translates back into the original data set. By this it is meant that the data from Bin k is added to Bin $k+1$ to create a single bin.

$$\eta = e^{\alpha_0 + \alpha_1 x_1 + \dots + \alpha_k x_k + \alpha_k x_{k+1} + \dots} \quad (4.9)$$

Step 5: Return to Step 1

Once the data set has been combined in the appropriate manner the entire process is repeated. This is done continually until there are no constraint violations or every bin has been combined.

4.5 Model and Constraints (With Baseline)

The general approach to this method remains the same with the usage of a baseline. The selection of the baseline is important, and in the cases of Versions 1 and 5 of the binning methods, should be Bin 2. The reason for this selection is because each bin is compared to the baseline bin. It is therefore sensible to select the least stressful bin that contains a significant number of aircraft. With the addition of the baseline comes the addition of constraints. These can be seen in Equation 4.10. It is shown that the addition of a baseline forces all alphas with a subscript greater than the baseline to be negative. Once these initial constraints have been created the remaining steps are the same for this method.

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{Max } L(\mathbf{\alpha}) \\ &\text{st } \alpha_i \geq \alpha_{i+1} \\ &\alpha_2 = 0 \\ &\mathbf{\alpha} = (\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n) \end{aligned} \quad (4.10)$$

5 APPLICATION OF MODELING APPROACH

To better illustrate the application of the constrained maximum likelihood approach, a real world example is used. The component and numbers have been masked for security, however the general approach remains. Throughout the course of this example the part under study is referred to Component A. The example focuses on a single component and covers all of the steps used to arrive at the final model.

Step 1 Run 1

The first step in this analysis was to run the ALTA model using all possible bins. Because ALTA was unable to process the model using all the Bins simultaneously a baseline approach was needed. After setting alpha for Bin 2 to zero, the model was run again and the following results were obtained.

Table 2: Alphas from Run 1

Bins	Bin 1	Bin 2	Bin 3	Bin 4	Bin 5	Bin 6	Bin 7
Alpha	-5.895	0	0.465	0.905	-1.277	-0.686	2.400

Step 2 Run 1

The corresponding constraint violations for this run are

located in Table 3.

Table 3: Violations from Run 1

Δ_1	Δ_2	Δ_3	Δ_4	Δ_5	Δ_6
5.8948	0.4652	0.44	-	0.5913	3.0856

Step 3 Run 1

From Table 3 it can be seen that the highest violation, the highlighted portion, comes from Δ_1 . When using Equations 4.6 it can be seen that k takes on a value of 1

Step 4 Run 1

Now that the highest violation has been determined, the additional constraint can be added. In this case it has been determined that Alpha 1 and 2 are equal to one another. This is derived from Equation 4.8. This combination is then applied to the raw data form the bins. For this case, Bins 1 and 2 are combined.

Step 5 Run 1

Because the new model in which Bins 1 and 2 and been combined has not been run, we must repeat this process. In the following runs only the numerical results are shown to expedite the process.

Run 2

From this run Bins 1, 2, and 3 are combined.

Table 4: Output from Run 2

Bins	1 to 2	3	4	5	6	7
Alphas	0	3.2684	2.5331	0.6823	0.4817	2.1091
Violations	Δ_1	Δ_2	Δ_3	Δ_4	Δ_5	
	3.2684	0.7353	3.2154	1.164	1.6274	

Run 3

From this run Bins 1, 2, 3, and 4 are combined.

Table 5: Output from Run 3

Bins	1 to 3	4	5	6	7
Alphas	0	1.482	-1.8669	-0.6926	0.5132
Violations	Δ_1	Δ_2	Δ_3	Δ_4	
	1.482	-3.3489	1.1743	1.2058	

Run 4

From the results of this run Bins 6 and 7 are combined.

Table 6: Output from Run 4

Bins	1 to 4	5	6	7
Alphas	0	-2.2214	-1.2531	0.3335
Violations	Δ_1	Δ_2	Δ_3	
	-2.2214	0.9683	1.5866	

Run 5

From this run Bins 5, 6, and 7 are combined

Table 7: Output from Run 5

Bins	1 to 4	5	6 to 7
Alphas	0	-2.2534	-0.8579
Violations	Δ_1	Δ_2	
	-2.2534	1.3955	

Run 6

All Conditions have been met, the final model can be obtained.

Table 8: Output from Run 6

Bins	1 to 4	5 to 7
Alphas	0	-1.0816
Violations	Δ_1	
	-1.0816	

Final Model

From the above steps, the final model can be assembled. It has been concluded that for this specific component only two aggregate bins are needed. These bins are the combination of Bins 1 through 4 and the combination of Bins 5 through 7. This grouping means that Bins 1 through 4 all impact the component in a similar manner and the same can be said about the second grouping. This finalized model can be seen in Equation 5.1. It can be seen that the alphas and binning groups are reflected in the model's scale parameter.

$$f(t) = \frac{\beta}{\eta} \left(\frac{t}{\eta} \right)^{\beta-1} e^{-\left(\frac{t}{\eta} \right)^\beta} \quad (5.1)$$

$$\eta = \eta_0 \exp(0 \times (x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + x_4) - 1.0816(x_5 + x_6 + x_7))$$

6 CONCLUSION

A general modeling approach has been developed to predict reliability for components with changing future stress levels. Since the stress variables are correlated, it is difficult to use them both in the model. Instead a new approach has been developed based on mission profile bins. While this approach is being applied to U.S. Navy systems, it is a general approach that could be adapted and used for many different applications.

REFERENCES

1. Hada, A., Coit, D., Agnello, M. and Megow, K. System Reliability Models with Stress Covariates for Changing Load Profiles. *Annual Reliability and Maintainability Symposium*, 2011.
2. Wang, Z., Kang R., and Xie, L.. Modeling a Failure Rate Model with the Number of Loading Applications as a Life Parameter. *China Mechanical Engineering*, 2009-2010.
3. Zhang, X., and Gockenbach, E.. Component Reliability Modeling of Distribution Systems Based on the

- Evaluation of Failure Statistics. *IEEE Transactions on Dielectrics and Electrical Insulation*, 2007, Vol. 14.
4. Wang, Z., Xie, L. and Bing, Li, B. Reliability Model of Failure-Dependent System with Frequency of Loading Taken into Account. *Journal of Northeastern University*, 2007.
 5. Zhang, X., Jiaosuo, and Gockenbach, E.. Reliability centered asset management for medium-voltage deteriorating electrical equipment based on Germany failure statistics. *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, 2009, Vol. 24.
 6. Prasad. P.V.N., Reliability models of repairable systems considering the effect of operating conditions. *Annual Reliability and Maintainability Symposium*, 2002.
 7. Attardi, G., and Pulcini, G. A Mixed-Weibull regression model for the analysis of automotive warranty data. *Reliability Engineering and System Safety*, 2005, vol. 87.
 8. Zhang, J., and Wang, R., Life prediction for vacuum fluorescent display using maximum likelihood estimation. *Journal of Southeast University (English Edition)*, 2006, Vol. 25.

BIOGRAPHIES

Dona Johnson
NAVAIR, Dept of Navy
Highway 547,
Lakehurst, NJ 08733 USA

dona.johnson@navy.mil

Dona Johnson is a Mechanical Engineer in the Reliability and Maintainability branch at NAVAIR. She received her BS and MS in mechanical engineering and MEM from Rowan University. She has worked for the Navy for over six years in both support equipment design and aircraft launch and recovery equipment (ALRE).

David W. Coit, PhD
Department of Industrial & Systems Engineering, Rutgers University
96 Frelinghuysen Road
Piscataway, NJ 08854 USA

coit@rutgers.edu

David W. Coit is a Professor in the Department of Industrial & Systems Engineering at Rutgers University. He received a BS degree in mechanical engineering from Cornell University, and MBA from Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute, and MS & Ph.D. in industrial engineering from the University of Pittsburgh. He also has over 10 years of experience working for IIT Research Institute (IITRI), Rome, NY. He is a member of IIE and INFORMS.

Robert Kosaka
Department of Industrial & Systems Engineering, Rutgers University
96 Frelinghuysen Road
Piscataway, NJ 08854 USA

kosakamaka@gmail.com

Robert Kosaka is a current MS student at Rutgers University studying Reliability and Quality Engineering. His undergraduate work was also completed at Rutgers University, where he studied Industrial Engineering. Over the past year he has worked with NAVAIR to develop predictive reliability models to support the recovery and launcher service life management program.

Keith Megow
NAVAIR, Dept of Navy
Highway 547
Lakehurst, NJ 08733 USA

keith.megow@navy.mil

Keith Megow graduated from Rutgers University in 1983 with a BSME and New Jersey Institute of Technology in 2002 with an MSEE. He worked for the Naval Air Propulsion Center, Trenton, NJ from 1983-1997 as a test engineer. Then from 1997 to 2008, he worked at Fort Monmouth in the area of signals intelligence. From 2008 to present he has worked at the Naval Air Warfare Center, Lakehurst, NJ in the field of reliability and maintainability for a variety of aircraft launch and recovery programs.